

PRIME PETE

PRIMARY EDUCATION PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER EDUCATION

Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

Attilio Carraro, Giampaolo Santi, Francis Ries,
Manolis Adamakis, Alina Lemling

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Technical sheet

Title: Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

Authors: Attilio Carraro, Giampaolo Santi, Francis Ries, Manolis Adamakis and Alina Lemling

Number of pages: 19

Year: 2023

Cite as: Carraro, A., Santi, G., Ries, F., Adamakis, M., & Lemling, A. (2023). Exploitation and Sustainability Plan [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #10].
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10031425>.

Project: Primary Education Physical Education Teacher Education

Project Coordinator: Claude Scheuer (until February 2023), Alina Lemling (from February 2023)

Funder: European Commission

Programme: Erasmus+ Key Action 2: Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices
2020

Action Type: Strategic Partnerships for Higher Education

Reference: 2020-1-LU01-KA203-063257

Timeline: December 2020 – August 2023

Project Sheet: <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/projects/eplu-project-details/#project/2020-1-LU01-KA203-063257>

For further information on the PRIME PETE Project please follow the link:

Website: <https://www.primepete.com/>

Project partners:

The authors wish to acknowledge the contribution of the Primary Education Physical Education Teacher Education (PRIME PETE) project team for the development of the outputs here referenced for PRIME PETE (2023).

No.	Institution	Involved researchers
1	University of Luxembourg, Luxembourg	Claude Scheuer (until February 23), Alina Lemling (from Feb 23), Manolis Adamakis (from June 21), Richard Bailey (May-December 21), Sandra Heck (until June 22)
2	Libera Universita di Bolzano, Italy	Attilio Carraro, Partizia Tortella (until March 21), Giampaolo Santi (from December 21)
3	Universidad de Sevilla	Francis Ries, Matilde Mora Fernández (until March 22)
4	Faculdade de Motricidade Humana (FMH), Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal	Marcos Onofre, Nuno Ferro, António Rodrigues, João Martins
5	Dublin City University, Ireland	Susan Marron, Frances Murphy
6	Trnavska Univerzita v Trnave, Slovakia	Dana Masarykova, Jana Labudova
7	European Physical Education Association [EUPEA], Luxembourg	Tamas Csanyi, Yiannis Gryparis (until September 21), Martin Holzweg, Rose-Marie Repond

Disclaimer: The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use, which may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of Contents

Technical sheet	1
1. Summary of the PRIME PETE project.....	4
2. Produced results, content, and format of the intellectual outputs.....	5
2.1. The 10 Intellectual Outputs of the PRIME PETE project	5
2.2. Learning, Teaching and Training (LTT) activities in Brixen-Bressanone and Lisbon	6
2.3. National and international Multiplier Events	6
3. Methodology and implementation steps	8
4. Project goals and needs analysis.....	9
5. Division of work	11
6. Target groups and accessibility	13
7. Elements of innovation	14
8. Expected impact and transferability potential	14
9. Conclusions of the exploitation and sustainability plan	14
References	16

1. Summary of the PRIME PETE project

This report aims to provide an overview of the PRIME PETE project and to summarise how its intellectual outputs (IOs) can be useful and sustained in the future. The PRIME PETE project is built on the belief that Physical Education (PE) can produce benefits in physical, social, cognitive and emotional domains (e.g., Whitehead 2019; Young et al., 2020). As a school discipline, PE is considered to be effective for increasing accessibility to physical activities, increasing levels of physical activity (PA), as well as aiding young people gain sport skills necessary for continued involvement in being physically active (European Commission, 2008; European Parliament, 2016; MacPhail et al., 2018; Opstoel et al., 2020).

In the interest of the holistic development of children, the PRIME PETE project has focused on the formal education of primary PE teachers. PE teachers can be classified as generalist or specialist teachers: generalist primary school teachers teach all subjects of the curriculum in many countries, while other countries have PE specialist teachers, who support generalist teachers in some countries (see Hardman et al., 2014; Ries et al., 2023). A quality PE teacher education (PETE) academic study programme for primary school should provide prospective teachers as lifelong learners with a deep knowledge of PE and a set of reflective, pedagogical and didactic skills and professional dispositions that allow them to design and provide quality physical education (QPE) for all pupils (AIESEP, 2014; UNESCO, 2015).

According to the PRIME PETE project partners: “The ideal primary PE teacher is competent, analytically reflective and professionally effective and cognisant of one’s health and well-being. As the role of primary PE teacher is vital for an effective promotion of PA and healthy lifestyle in school settings, a primary PETE study programme should also include these aspects” (Ries et al., 2023, p.8). Hence, the aim of the PRIME PETE project has been to bring together European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), as well as other stakeholders active in primary PETE, in order to promote their cooperation and state suggestions to qualify PRIME PE teachers. With this in mind, the 7 project partners of the PRIME PETE (see Figure 1) shared their knowledge and resources to produce the 10 IOs that have been produced for the accomplishment of the project.

Figure 1 PRIME PETE project partners.

2. Produced results, content, and format of the intellectual outputs

In the attempt to present IO #10 as a stand-alone document that is easily readable for the interested parties, the 10 IOs and the other activities carried out during the project are summarised in the present section with the goal to provide an overview of the previous steps in the PRIME PETE project. The IOs are presented in the Subsection 2.1, whereas the following subsections aim to inform the readers about the other activities that allowed to the accomplishment of the PRIME PETE project. Those are the Learning, Teaching and Training (LTT) activities, involving university teacher-students, and the Multiplier Events, involving teacher educators.

2.1. The 10 Intellectual Outputs of the PRIME PETE project

The 10 IOs that allowed the accomplishment of the PRIME PETE project are presented in Table 1. Table 1 reports the title of each IO, the timeframe within it was accomplished, and the partners leading and co-leading each task. The IOs are made available to the interested parties in form of reports, a handbook, slides and other course materials. The output content is presented in English language, and is downloadable from the PRIME PETE platform (<https://www.primepete.com>). The platform, launched online in June 2023, will remain online and updated for at least the following ten years (2023-2033).

Table 1 PRIME PETE intellectual output title, the timeframe of their accomplishment, and leading and co-leading partners.

<i>Intellectual output</i>	<i>Timeframe</i>	<i>Leading partner</i>	<i>Co-leading partner</i>
IO1: Overview on Primary Physical Education Teachers' Education in Europe	Dec 2020-Dec 2022	Trnava University	University of Luxembourg
IO2: Recommendations on Primary PETE	Dec 2020-Dec 2022	FMH, University of Lisbon	University of Luxembourg
IO3: Primary PE teacher profile	Mar 2021-Dec 2022	European Physical Education Association (EUPEA)	University of Seville
IO4: Theoretical and methodological framework	Jun 2021-Dec 2022	University of Seville	Dublin City University

IO5: Modules and micromodules for Primary PE courses	Sep 2021-Feb 2023	Dublin City University	FMH, University of Lisbon; Trnava University
IO6: Development of an evaluation method	Sep 2021-Feb 2023	University of Luxembourg	European Physical Education Association (EUPEA)
IO7: Evaluation of modules and micromodules	Dec 2021-Jun 2023	University of Luxembourg	European Physical Education Association (EUPEA)
IO8: Handbook and guidance for the implementation of PRIME PETE programmes	Nov 2022-Aug 2023	Trnava University	FMH, University of Lisbon; Dublin City University
IO9: Open course platform	Mar 2023-Aug 2023	University of Luxembourg	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano
IO10: Exploitation and sustainability plan	Mar 2023-Jul 2023	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano	University of Luxembourg

2.2. Learning, Teaching and Training (LTT) activities in Brixen-Bressanone and Lisbon

The Learning, Teaching and Training (LTT) activities, held in Brixen-Bressanone (Italy, 6-11 June 2022) and in Lisbon (Portugal, 11-17 September 2022), were organised, respectively, by the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano and the “Faculdade de Motricidade Humana” (FMH) of the University of Lisbon. Each project partner invited university students enrolled in their institutions to take part in the LTT. Students were attending PE, sport sciences, primary education and related courses in their respective universities.

During the LTTs students were asked to attend and actively participate in the micromodules proposed by each project partner as part of the IO5 (Marron et al., 2023). Finally, they were asked to evaluate content and delivery of each micromodule. Teacher educators also provided their evaluation of the micromodules (Adamakis et al., 2023; Adamakis & Scheuer, 2023).

2.3. National and international Multiplier Events

In conclusion of the project (May and June 2023), National Multiplier Events (MEs) were organised by each project partner in their respective countries in order to present the results to the interested parties, i.e., teacher educators, scholars, policy makers and relevant stakeholders (see Table 2). Additionally, an

Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

International Multiplier Event (IME) was held in Trnava (23rd June 2023) to reach an international audience. Collectively, these MEs constitutes an important part of the dissemination of the project results.

Table 2 Summary of national and international Multiplier Events.

Country	Location and date	Attendance	Organising partner
Italy	Verona, 19 th May 2023 (hybrid)	16 participants	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano
Ireland	Dublin, 8 th June 2023	37 participants	Dublin City University
Trnava	Trnava, 9 th June 2023	18 participants	Trnava University
Italy	14 th June 2023 (online)	20 participants	Free University of Bozen-Bolzano
Portugal	Lisbon, 28 th June 2023	16 participants	FMH, University of Lisbon
Luxembourg	Belval, 4 th July 2023 (hybrid)	20 participants	University of Luxembourg
International (held in Slovakia)	Trnava, 23 rd June 2023	28 participants	EUPEA
Total number of participants:		155 participants	

3. Methodology and implementation steps

The methodology for the implementation of the exploitation and sustainability plan has been structured according to 4 steps:

1. A clear rationale and objectives of exploitation and sustainability;
2. A strategy to identify which results to disseminate to which audiences;
3. Allocation of tasks and responsibilities;
4. Monitoring of the activities.

The first three steps have already been described in the previous sections (see Sections 3, 4, and 7, respectively). The rationale for the present exploitation and sustainability plan was discussed among partners in the Transnational Partner Meeting (TPM) held in Seville in November 2023. Following this, goals were defined through e-mail exchanges among the project partners. Partners were asked by the IO #10 leading partner to indicate their bullet points or objectives for the exploitation and sustainability plan. These points and objectives were therefore summarised by the leading partner and discussed together with the other partner in an online meeting held on Monday 22nd May 2023. During this meeting, strategies and allocation of tasks and responsibilities were also discussed among partners.

A final discussion was conducted during the last TPM of project planned in Trnava (21st and 22nd June 2023). Monitoring of the activities is performed independently by each responsible project partner, and continuing e-mail exchange among partners allows for updates and co-operation.

4. Project goals and needs analysis

A clear definition of the project goals is the first step for developing a sustainability plan. Based on these goals and on an analysis of needs, it is possible to plan the required activities and to share tasks among project partners and the wider community in order to make the PRIME PETE online platform sustainable over time and to further disseminate and build on the project results in the future.

Project partners agreed to some common goals for this project sustainability plan, specifically:

- (1) Launch of the website;
- (2) Maintenance of the website;
- (3) Reports of each IO, modules and handbook available on the website;
- (4) Presentation of results at national and international conferences and events;
- (5) Disseminate results through university newsletters, university websites, and relevant associations and organisations;
- (6) Include PRIME PETE micro-modules in existing university courses and Continuing Professional Development (CPD)

The launch of the website was planned for June 2023 and its maintenance is guaranteed for the following 10 years (2023-2033). The website (<https://www.primepete.com>) includes reports for all the 10 IOs, as well as a description of each module and micro-module proposed by the project partners, together with slides and further materials relating to each micro-module (Marron et al., 2023). Additionally, *a handbook and guidance material for the implementation of the primary PETE programme* (Masarykova, Lemling, et al., 2023) is available on the website in pdf format. Further tools and information regarding evaluation methods, derived from the IOs #6 & #7 (Adamakis & Scheuer, 2023; Adamakis et al., 2023), are also provided on the web platform.

The LTT activities and the national and international MEs organised within this project represented a consistent part of presentation and dissemination of the results. In fact, they provided an opportunity to reach relevant parties, such as teacher students, teacher educators, scholars and policy makers in the field of PE, and other relevant stakeholders. Teacher students will be future PE teachers or future teacher educators, and taking part in this project through LTT activities will help them have an overview of the current state of primary PE teacher education in Europe and of future directions. By taking part in the MEs, teacher educators (university professors or lecturers involved in delivering courses in related disciplines) gained the possibility to inform and maybe inspire their future university course programmes based on the work accomplished for the PRIME PETE project. Additionally, other interested parties involved in the MEs, like educators delivering CPD, can be inspired by the PRIME PETE results in order to align their programmes on those suggested by the present project (see Marron et al., 2023; Masarykova, Scheuer, et al., 2023; Onofre et al., 2023; Repond et al., 2023; Ries et al., 2023).

Leveraging on each partner network of organisations and stakeholders (e.g., associations, ministries, policy makers, stakeholders, and other relevant parties within schools and social bodies), further dissemination of results could be planned. For example, the web platform and the project results may be presented at relevant conferences (e.g., AIESEP annual conferences). Furthermore, results can be spread through the university newsletters by the project partners or through websites of other relevant associations (EUPEA, AIESEP). The final outputs are available online (besides the project website), in its definitive version as an open access resource under a respective license, on platforms such as the Erasmus+ results platform, researchgate.net, and other platforms that allow to assign a doi-number to the publication. International organisations, such as the European Commission, the UNESCO, and the OECD, have also been contacted to disseminate the project results.

Finally, each project partner has the opportunity to consider including the PRIME PETE modules and micro-modules in their existing university programmes, and CPD run by other institutions or associations. The division of work for reaching these goals is further described in the following Section of the present IO.

5. Division of work

In the present section, the division of work and tasks are outlined to facilitate the accomplishment of the goals identified by project partners for the exploitation and sustainability plan. The different partners were responsible for each goal indicated in Table 3.

Table 3 Division of work for the accomplishment of the IO #10.

Goal	Tasks	Leading partner
(1) Launch of the website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of contents; - Contacts with software developer 	University of Luxembourg for the definition of contents; Trnava University for the contacts with the software developer
(2) Website maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintenance of the website for the next 10 years 	Trnava University; Other project partners for providing relevant updates to the online materials
(3) Reports of each IO, modules and handbook available on the website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Refinement of reports for each IO for publication on the PRIME PETE website and other relevant platforms; - Refinement of modules template and related materials; - Upload of the material 	Each partner for their respective IOs and modules/micromodules; University of Luxembourg for uploading the material
(4) Presentation of results at national and international conferences and events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of LTTs; - Organisation of MEs; - Identification of relevant conferences in this field 	LTTs already completed by the University of Bozen-Bolzano and by the FMH, University of Lisbon; MEs organised by each project partner in their respective country (see subsection 2.3); All the partners are responsible to identify relevant

		<p>conferences organised in the future years</p> <p>Connecting results with EDUPASS (responsible Uni Seville?)</p> <p>Use outcomes for another EU funded project, proposed by Seville (?)</p>
<p>(5) Disseminate results through university, university websites, and relevant associations and organisations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communication through the University newsletter or via the University website; - Communication via websites of relevant association (AIESEP, EUPEA) - Further dissemination through institutional Social Media Profiles (e.g., Twitter, LinkedIn, ...) 	<p>Each project partner is responsible for their own University;</p> <p>The University of Bozen-Bolzano is responsible to contact the AIESEP website manager to publish information regarding the PRIME PETE project;</p> <p>EUPEA is responsible to publish information regarding the PRIME PETE project on their website</p>
<p>(6) Include PRIME PETE micro-modules in existing university courses and CPD</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include micromodules presented by the other PRIME PETE project partners in each partners' respective university course; - Propose PRIME PETE modules and micromodules to non-academic educational institutions 	<p>Each partner takes into consideration the inclusion of PRIME PETE micromodules in their university course;</p> <p>Each partner is responsible to involve relevant educational institutions in their own countries</p>

6. Target groups and accessibility

The target groups addressed by this exploitation and sustainability plan encompass teacher education institutions, teacher educators, primary teachers teaching primary PE, Non-governmental organisations (NGOs; like research associations, teacher associations, ...), stakeholders and policy makers in charge of teacher education.

The project's target group members, as well as the main key stakeholders listed in Table 4, have received information and will be updated on the project's scope, progress, outputs, news through a variety of means, such as emails, social media posts, phone calls, invitations, meetings, based on each partner's preference and possible actions and always in accordance with GDPR regulations. Table 4 provides examples of each target groups and how to reach them.

Table 4 PRIME PETE project target groups.

Main target group	Example	Accessibility
Teacher education institutions	Universities, organisations and associations providing CPD for primary PE teacher	Contact through social network of the project partners
Teacher educators	University professors and lecturers, trainers and professionals in charge of primary PE teachers' education	Involvement of these groups in pertinent events, such as the LTTs, the national and international MEs, and presentation at relevant conferences and events
Primary teachers teaching primary PE	In-service primary teachers and teacher-students	Participation to CPD and university courses
Non-governmental organisations	National associations for PE (e.g., SISMeS and CAPDI in Italy, Consejo COLEF in Spain, IPPEA in Ireland, ...)	Contact through each project partner social network
Stakeholders	Stakeholders in the field of physical activity and health promotion, such as companies providing equipment and technologies for PE classes, physical activity promotion, and fitness monitoring	Contact through each project partner social network

Policy makers in charge of teacher education	National ministries of education, the European Commission, the UNESCO, the OECD, the WHO	Formal contact from the project partners
---	--	--

7. Elements of innovation

This PRIME PETE exploitation and sustainability plan represents an innovative document to facilitate cooperation and networking among HEI and other institutions active in the field of primary PETE in Europe. To date, no published documents exist that presented a common framework for primary PETE, a teacher profile for a primary teacher of PE or a thematic programme that could be shared across providers of primary PETE in Europe. One recent book reviewed and summarise PE teacher education practices in different European countries (MacPhail et al,2019). The PRIME PETE project goes beyond an overview of PETE in Europe and proposes a PE teacher profile, along with recommendations and materials for the education of PE teachers.

8. Expected impact and transferability potential

The tasks indicated in this exploitation and sustainability plan represent a roadmap for the sustainable dissemination of the project outcomes. Furthermore, the present plan may lead to further cooperation amongst project partners and with external partners and HEIs active in the field of primary PETE, thus facilitating students and teachers' mobility in Europe in this study field.

The expected impact of the IO #10 can be synthesised in three points:

- (1) To make the PRIME PETE outputs visible to target groups through dissemination strategies;
- (2) To give continuity to the network by maintaining contacts among the project partners and developing new partnerships;
- (3) To facilitate the mobility of students, lecturer and in-service teachers across Europe and the exchange of knowledge and perspectives.

9. Conclusions of the exploitation and sustainability plan

With regards to the accomplishment of the tasks indicated in this IO #10, the PRIME PETE project partners agree to the following three principles:

1. **Shared responsibility:** Each partner is responsible for the promotion of the project to its network.

Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

2. **Flexibility:** The activities theorized by the plan could be adjusted by each partner according to the context in which each partner operates, but the minimum standards proposed should be maintained.
3. **Efficiency:** Each partner commits to achieve the best result in terms of visibility with the available resources.

As the dissemination is regarded as an active and targeted process, the exploitation and sustainability plan must be considered as an evolving document.

References

- Adamakis, M., & Scheuer, C. (2023). *Evaluation study and report* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #7].
- Adamakis, M., Scheuer, C., Carraro, A., & Santi, G. (2023). *Method and tool to evaluate the PETE course modules and micro-modules* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #6].
- AIESEP (2014). *Position Statement on Physical Education Teacher Education*. Available on: <https://aiesep.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/11/2014-AIESEP-Position-Statement-on-Physical-Education-Teacher-Education.pdf>
- European Commission (2008). *EU Physical Activity Guidelines. Recommended Policy Actions in Support of Health-Enhancing Physical Activity*. Brussels: European Commission.
- European Parliament (2016). *Physical Education in EU schools*. Brussels: European Parliament.
- Hardman, K. ... et al. (2014). *World-wide survey of school physical education: final Report*. Paris, France: UNESCO.
- MacPhail, A., Bulca, Y., Carraro, A., & Avşar, Z. (2018). Initial Post-Primary Physical Education Teacher Education: A Comparative Exploration across European Countries. *International Journal of Sports and Physical Education (IJSPE)*, 4 (4), 15-22. DOI: 10.20431/2454-6380.0404003
- MacPhail, A., Tannehill, D., & Avsar, Z. (2019). *European Physical Education Teacher Education practices*. Meyer & Meyer Sport.
- Marron, S., Murphy, F., Onofre, M., Martins, J., Ferro, N., Rodrigues, A., Carraro, A., Santi, G., Scheuer, C., & Lemling, A. (2023). *Modular Primary PETE programme consisting of course modules and micro-modules* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #5].
- Masarykova, D., Lemling, A., Marron, S., & Murphy, F. (2023). *Handbook and guidance material for the implementation of the primary PETE programme* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #8].

- Masarykova, D., Scheuer, C., Lemling, A., Adamakis, M., Heck, S., Bailey, R., Onofre, M., Martins, J., Ferro, N., Rodrigues, A., Carraro, A., Tortella, P., & Csányi, T. (2023). *Overview on Primary Physical Education Teacher Education in Europe* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #1].
- Onofre, M., Ferro, N., Martins, J., Rodrigues, A., Carraro, A., Scheuer, C., Bailey, R., Adamakis, M., Heck, S., & Lemling, A. (2023). *Recommendations on Primary Physical Education Teacher Education* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #2].
- Opstoel, K., Chapelle, L., Prins, F. J., De Maester, A., Haerens, L., van Tartwijk, J. De Martelaer, K. (2020). Personal and social development in physical education and sports: A review study. *European Physical Education Review*, 26(4), 797-813.
- Repond, R.-M., Csányi, T., Scheuer, C., Ries, F., Carraro, A., Onofre, M., Martins, J., Ferro, N., & Rodrigues, A. (2023). *Primary Physical Education Teacher Profile* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #3].
- Ries, F., Carraro, A., Santi, G., & Scheuer, C. (2023). *Theoretical and Methodological Framework for Primary Physical Education Teacher Education in Europe* [PRIME PETE Project - Report Intellectual Output #4].
- UNESCO (2015). *Quality Physical Education: Guidelines for Policymakers*. Paris, France: UNESCO Publishing. Retrieved May 31, 2023, from: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000231101>
- Whitehead, M. (2019). *Physical literacy across the world*. Routledge.
- Young, L., O'Connor, & Alfrey, L. (2020). Physical literacy: a concept analysis. *Sport, Education and Society*, DOI: 10.1080/13573322.2019.1677586